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A SHORT REVIEW ON ALOE VERA

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1. Introduction

Aloe Vera is an important and traditional medicinal plant belonging to the family Liliaceae. Aloe Vera is known by several names like Ghrit Kumari, Kunvar pathu and Indian Aloe and is widely cultivated because of its wide adaptability and use as a medicinal plant especially in dry areas. It is indigenous to Africa and Mediterranean countries. Nearly there are about 150 species in Aloe. Among this species, there is only one variety that has a legendary medical reputation dating back thousands of years, it is the Aloe Vera. Aloe is supposed to be derived from the Arabic “alloeh” meaning “bitter” because of bitter liquid found in the leaves. Aloe can be a good substitute to the synthetic ingredients now being used in cosmetic industry. Aloe Vera is the oldest medicinal plant ever known and the most applied medicinal plant worldwide.

Rank	Scientific Name and Common Name
Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Tracheobionta
Superdivision	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Liliopsida
Subclass	Liliidae
Order	Liliales
Family	Aloaceae
Genus	Aloe L
Species	<i>Aloe barbadensis</i> Mill

Table: **Taxonomic Classification of Aloe vera** (Sánchez-Machado, 2017)

2. History

Aloe vera has been used for medicinal purposes in several cultures for millennia: Greece, Egypt, India, Mexico, Japan and China. Egyptian queens Nefertiti and Cleopatra used it as part of their regular beauty regimes. Alexander the Great, and Christopher Columbus used it to treat soldiers' wounds. The first reference to Aloe vera in English was a translation by John Goodyew in A.D.

FIGURE 1 PHYSIOLOGICAL MAP OF WORLD

Australia **Grece** **Egypt** **India** **Mexico** **Japan** **Chaina**

1655 of Dioscorides' Medical treatise *De Materia Medica* by the early 1800s, Aloe vera was in use as a laxative in the United States, but in the mid-1930s, a turning point occurred when it was successfully used to treat chronic and severe radiation dermatitis. (Amar Surjushe, 2008)

3. Botanical Characteristics

The cactus-like succulent aloe vera belongs to the genus of the liliaceous plants. The plant is either stem-less or very short-stemmed (stem up to 25 cm long) with an average about 20 leaves in a

straight, dense rosette. The leaves grow to up to 40 – 50 cm long and 6 – 7 cm wide. The leaves are rather thick, fleshy, water retaining; concave on the top side, grey-green often reddish and young plants are often speckled. The underside of the leaf is convex with a pale pink rim that is dressed with 2 mm long thorny teeth spaced at every 10 – 20 mm. One leaf can weigh as much as 1.5 to 2 kg. The succulent leaf of the aloe is an adaptation to the very dry conditions of its habitat. The roots of the aloe are relatively short and lay flat embedded in the earth. The inflorescence is simple or a simple or double raceme and grows up to 60 – 90 cm. The raceme is dense, cylindrical and narrowing towards the top. The racemes grow up to 40 cm long. The perianths are white, the blossoms about 3 cm long and bright yellow to red. The fruit of the plant are loculicidal capsules. The aloe grows numerous adventitious buds which the plant later uses for reproduction in a vegetative way. (Atherton)

3.1 Active components with its properties: (Amar Surjushe, 2008)

Aloe vera contains 75 potentially active constituents: vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugars, lignin, saponins, salicylic acids and amino acids.⁴⁻⁶

Vitamins: It contains vitamins A (beta-carotene), C and E, which are antioxidants. It also contains vitamin B12, folic acid, and choline. Antioxidant neutralizes free radicals.

Enzymes: It contains 8 enzymes: amylase, alkaline phosphatase, amylase, bradykinase, carboxypeptidase, catalase, cellulase, lipase, and peroxidase. Bradykinase helps to reduce excessive inflammation when applied to the skin topically, while others help in the breakdown of sugars and fats.

Minerals: It provides calcium, chromium, copper, selenium, magnesium, manganese, potassium, sodium and zinc. They are essential for the proper functioning of various enzyme systems in different metabolic pathways and few are antioxidants.

Sugars: It provides monosaccharides (glucose and fructose) and polysaccharides: (glucomannans/polymannose). These are derived from the mucilage layer of the plant and are known as mucopolysaccharides. The most prominent monosaccharide is mannose-6-phosphate, and the most common polysaccharides are called glucomannans [beta-(1,4)-acetylated mannan]. Acemannan, a prominent glucomannan has also been found. Recently, a glycoprotein with antiallergic properties, called alprogen and novel anti-inflammatory compound, C-glucosyl chromone, has been isolated from Aloe vera gel.^{7,8}

Anthraquinones: It provides 12 anthraquinones, which are phenolic compounds traditionally known as laxatives. Aloin and emodin act as analgesics, antibacterials and antivirals.

Fatty acids: It provides 4 plant steroids; cholesterol, campesterol, β -sisosterol and lupeol. All these have anti-inflammatory action and lupeol also possesses antiseptic and analgesic properties.

Hormones: Auxins and gibberellins that help in wound healing and have anti-inflammatory action.

Others: It provides 20 of the 22 human required *amino acids* and 7 of the 8 essential amino acids. It also contains salicylic acid that possesses anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties. Lignin, an inert substance, when included in topical preparations, enhances penetrative effect of the other ingredients into the skin. Saponins that are the soapy substances form about 3% of the gel and have cleansing and antiseptic properties.

4. Uses Of Aloe Vera

Aloe Vera is referred for Ayurvedic treatments where it is useful in the treatment of burns, blood disorders, chronic constipation, skin diseases, and as eye drops for relief in sore eyes and redness as well as bleeding and healing of wounds, etc. It plays an important role in gerontology and rejuvenation. Aloe Vera is full of medicinal properties & it is effective in treating various body ailments. (Dalia I. Sanchez-Machado, 2017)

- Medical and Cosmetic Benefits
- Used in number of lotions, creams, gels and shampoos.
- As diet supplement or directly.
- Control the stomach acids and maintain balance in the stomach.
- Improve immune system.
- Stimulates tissues.
- Helpful for diabetes
- Absorb nutrients and neutralizing toxic and bad elements.

4.1 Health Benefits Of Aloe Vera

Below are the some of the health benefits and medicinal values of Aloe Vera.

- Aloe Vera is an anti-biotic, anti-microbial, anti-bacterial, disinfectant, anti-biotic, anti-septic, germicidal, anti-fungal and anti-viral.
- Aloe Vera is excellent for the skin treatments/cosmetic use.
- Aloe Vera is extensively used in treatment of urine related problems, ulcers and pimples.
- Aloe Vera is good source of vitamins and minerals.
- Aloe Vera is high in amino acids and fatty acids.
- Aloe Vera is a well-known adaptogen.
- Aloe Vera helps with digestion.
- Aloe Vera helps in detoxification process.
- Aloe Vera is heart healthy.
- Aloe Vera helps in boosting the Immune system

4.2. Side Effects

Topical: It may cause redness, burning, stinging sensation and rarely generalized dermatitis in sensitive individuals. Allergic reactions are mostly due to anthraquinones, such as aloin and barbaloin. It is best to apply it to a small area first to test for possible allergic reaction.

Oral: Abdominal cramps, diarrhea, red urine, hepatitis, dependency or worsening of constipation. Prolonged use has been reported to increase the risk of colorectal cancer. Laxative effect may cause electrolyte imbalances (low potassium levels).

Contraindication: Contraindicated in cases of known allergy to plants in the Liliaceae family. **Pregnancy and breastfeeding:** Oral aloe is not recommended during pregnancy due to theoretical stimulation of uterine contractions, and in breastfeeding mothers, it may sometime causes gastrointestinal distress in the nursing infant.

5. Climatic Requirements

Basically, Aloe Vera is a warm tropical crop. Aloe Vera can grow in various climatic conditions. This can be successfully grown in low rainfall regions and dry areas with warm humid conditions. This plant is very sensitive to extreme cold conditions. This plant thrives best on dry sandy soils

in the regions where lower rainfall is expected. This plant cannot tolerate frost and cool climatic conditions. Well drained laterite to loamy soils is suited for aloe cultivation. The soil pH must be ranged from 7.0 to 8.5. Commercial cultivation can be done in regions having 25 – 40°C. (Aloe Vera Farming Guide)

5.1. Land Preparation

As Aloe Vera is a shallow rooted crop; it is not required deep plough during land preparation. One or two ploughing should be given followed by harrowing based on soil type and climate. Make sure to level the land after ploughing. Make beds or suitable plot sizes considering good slopes for water drainage system and irrigation. Any organic matter like well rotten farm yard manure of 10 to 15 tonnes per hectare can be supplemented for better crop growth and yield. This FYM also results in better moisture holding capacity and improves soil texture.

6. Propagation and Planting Method

In Aloe Vera farming, propagation is done through root suckers / rhizome cuttings. In case of root sucking propagation, the process should be done by selecting medium size root suckers and carefully digging without damaging mother plant at the base. This can be directly planted in the main land. In case of rhizome cutting propagation, after harvesting the crop, digging out the underground rhizome and making about 6 cm length cuttings with two to three nodes on them is advised. After that it has to be placed on prepared sand beds. Once sprouts are popping up, it has to be transplanted into main field. Usually about 15000 suckers are required for 1 acre of nursery.

∴ Propagation Method - Pups (root suckers)

7. Planting Density & Spacing In Aloe Vera Farming

Planting can be done through the year if there is irrigation facility. However, planting right during rainy season (from July to August in India) would be considered best. Plant density of 10,000 to 10,500 suckers is required to cover 1 acre land or 25,000 suckers per 1 hectare land. Dig the pits of 14 to 15 cm deep and plant the suckers at 60 cm x 60 cm apart. Soil around root zone should be pressed firmly so that there won't be any water stagnation. (SHAHRIER, 2017)

8. Intercultural Operations

8.1. Weed Control/Inter Cultural Operations

It is one of the best crop management practices to keep the field weed free. This also helps in saving manures, fertilizers and irrigation. 2 to 3 hand weedings should be carried followed by light hoeing in a year. Carry out the first weeding and hoeing should be carried within a 4 weeks after planting the suckers. Subsequent years require 1 or 2 weedings with light hoeing to keep the weed growth in control. Destroy any diseased plants. Dried stakes should be removed regularly.

8.2. Irrigation System

Aloe Vera crop can be grown both under rainfed and irrigated conditions. Irrigation should be carried out immediately after planting the suckers. Couple of irrigations in hot summer weather will result in good yield. In rainy season, avoiding water logging in the field is advised as this crop is sensitive to water stagnation.

9. Manures And Fertilizers

As part of the land preparation, applying 15 to 20 tonnes/ha of well rotten farm yard manure (FYM) is advised. Thereafter the same dose of farm yard manure should be applied every year. As basal dose (forming or belonging to a bottom layer or base), fertilizers like NPK in the ratio of 50:50:50 kg per hectare should be applied.

10. Harvesting Tasks In Aloe Vera Farming

Aloe Vera crop will become ready for harvesting from second year after planting. Fresh leaves of 3 or 4 can be picked. Picking up leaves should be done during morning or evening times. Three harvests can be carried in one year time. This crop is a labor intensive crop. After harvesting leaves, again they re-generate up to 5 years after planting. Not only leaves, side suckers can be harvested for using in planting material.

11. Post Harvesting Tasks In Aloe Vera Farming

After harvesting the fresh leaves, care should be taken for drying the leaves. Usually harvested crop is allowed to loose the moisture in the field itself before transporting. To prevent any mould growth, leaves should be kept dry and cool. Use of concrete floor is useful in stacking or storing them.

12. Economic Life Of Aloe Vera

Commercial yield of Aloe Vera can be obtained from second to fifth year. Thereafter, field should be re-planted. Harvesting can be done with sharp sickle. Making sure to use viscous gel from the

9 cut end dries up before packing and marketing also need to assure only fully developed mature leaves are harvested for juice extraction.

13. Yield / Output Per Hectare Of Aloe Vera

Well, yield of any crop depends in cultivar, soil type and fertility, plant age and other crop management practices. An average yield of 40 to 45 tonnes of thick leaves can be obtained per 1 hectare land cultivation. ∴ 1 hectare land = 40 to 45 tonnes of output 4.1.2. BOTTOM LINE OF ALOE VERA FARMING Excellent plant for cultivation in the dry and regions with less annual rainfall and once planted, it gives the yield/output for 5 years.

∴ Once planted = 5 years of continuous output

14. Cultivation Procedure & Major Countries Produces/Exports Aloe Vera

Aloe vera has been widely grown as an attractive plant. The species is popular with modern gardeners as a putatively medicinal plant and for its interesting flowers, form, and succulence. This succulence enables the species to survive in areas of low natural rainfall, making it ideal for rockeries and other low water-use gardens. The species is hardy in zones 8–11, although it is intolerant of very heavy frost or snow. The species is relatively resistant to most insect pests, though spider mites, mealy bugs, scale insects, and aphid species may cause a decline in plant health. This plant has gained the Royal Horticultural Society's Award of Garden Merit. In pots, the species requires well-drained, sandy potting soil and bright, sunny conditions; however, Aloe plants can burn under too much sun or shrivel when the pot does not drain water. The use of a good-quality commercial propagation mix or packaged "cacti and succulent mix" is recommended, as they allow good drainage. Terra cotta pots are preferable as they are porous. Potted plants should be allowed to completely dry before re-watering. When potted, Aloes can 10 become crowded with "pups" growing from the sides of the "mother plant". Plants that have become crowded should be divided and repotted to allow room for further growth and help prevent pest infestations. During winter, Aloe Vera may become dormant, during which little moisture is required. In areas that receive frost or snow, the species is best kept indoors or in heated glasshouses. There is large-scale agricultural production of Aloe Vera is done in the following countries; 1. Australia, 2. Cuba, 3. The Dominican Republic, 4. China, 5. Mexico, 6. India, 7. Jamaica, 8. Kenya, 9. Tanzania 10. South Africa, 11. USA. Global demand has risen exponentially for Aloe Vera. USA, China, Korea, Japan, Australia and most parts of Europe has shown a considerable demand for finished Aloe Vera products. Trade in finished products containing aloe ingredients, are estimated to be over \$35 billion globally.

15. Pest In Aloe Vera

Spider Mites

The article also addressed spider mites. The mite that finds aloes delectable is the red spider mite. If you have an infestation of these, you will see small, pale markings on the surface of the aloe leaves. Aloes do not like these mites at all. Even flowers may be distorted, as the mites attack the emerging flower stalks.

Visible mites like these are easily contained by a sprinkling of insecticide powder in the centers of plants. The mites succumb to most insecticidal spray chemicals, as well. (Williams, 2020)

Figure 2 Spider Mites in Aloe Vera

Snout Beetles

Next on our list of pests is the snout beetle. This is aloe enemy No. 1, so quick action is required when you find these insects on your plants. The beetle, which can be up to 3/4 inch long, aims at the center of an aloe plant. It wedges itself between the leaves to insert its snout and drink the leaf sap. This leaves a telltale dark spot that dries into a pea-sized dry spot with a puncture mark in the middle.

Once the beetles have mated, eggs are deposited at the base of a leaf. The newly hatched larvae bore straight into the stem, where they spend the remainder of their larvae cycle. The rot and destruction caused by the larvae are what eventually kills the aloe.

Physically removing and killing the beetles or a sprinkle of insecticidal powder should take care of the mature beetles, if they have not been there too long. The number of bore holes and their

distance from the center of the plant will tell, at a glance, how long the beetles have been active. A large number of bore holes away from the center of the plant almost certainly means there are beetle larvae destroying the plant from inside. (Williams, 2020)

If this is the case, you have few options. If the plant is small, a good trash can is in order. If the plant is large, start cutting the stalk of the plant above the infestation. If more bore holes exist, cut some more. When you do not see any more holes, dip the stalk in rooting hormone, let it dry for a short time and see if it will root. A good systemic.

FIGURE 3 SNOUT BEETLES

Gall Mites

Another mite is particularly attracted to aloes. This is the gall mite. If you have an infestation of these little buggers, your aloes have a condition called gall cancer. Very often, the first sign of gall mites is a new but crooked flower cluster that emerges from a plant. Upon closer inspection, you may see the first signs of frilly growth on the flower stalk, which develops into unsightly galls on the small flower stalks that form the cluster as it matures. The same galls may also start as an irregular growth on the bases of older leaves, often where an earlier flower stalk has dried. Tree aloes are often the source of infestation. Huge galls form on old flower stalks and, if left untreated, can spread their inhabitants for many years. (Williams, 2020)

The gall mites travel through the air. Cut away the affected tissue with a sharp blade and treat the cut with a strong solution of aphicide or other systemic insecticide. The whole plant can be sprayed with the manufacturer's recommended solution of the same insecticide a day or so later. Aloes that touch an infected plant are particularly vulnerable.

FIGURE 4 GALL MITES

16. Diseases Of Aloe Vera

Basal Stem Rot

Now that the critters are out of the way, we turn our attention to diseases. The first and most familiar disease is basal stem rot. The result of cold and wet conditions, this condition leads to rotting stems. Aloe tissues affected by basal stem rot turn black or reddish brown.

It is possible to take a stem cutting above the rotten portion to save pieces of the plant. (As you can see in the picture), this plant is a goner. The rot travels up the stem, so early detection is a must. (Williams, 2020)

Figure 5 Basal Stem Rot

Aloe Rust

The next disease on the list is aloe rust. Caused by the fungi *Phakopsora pachyphiza* and *P. meibomia*, this fungal infection causes black or brown circular spots on the aloe leaves. The fungus invades the outer leaf structure and oxidizes the organic compounds in the leaf structure called phenols. The result is a spot that becomes blackened and hard. This rust also can occur on haworthia and gasteria leaves.

Aloe rust is a fungal infection that invades leaf structure and forms hard, blackened spots.

The good news is that this condition does not kill the plant, and new growth will not show signs of the rust. Most aloes lose their leaves as they grow. When they fall off, throw them in the trash.

Many plant species can serve as hosts for these fungi. Some have built up immunity, while the aloes, haworthias and gasterias have not. The spores of the fungi are carried by the wind and can travel a long distance. The conditions that favor infection are extended periods of leaf wetness and a temperature range of 60 to 82 degrees F. Temperatures above 86 degrees prevent development of the disease.

Spores are produced 10 days after infection and released about three weeks after that. As long as the environment is moist with moderate temperatures, spores will be generated.

There are some ways to prevent aloe rust from occurring. First is to not let water stay on the leaves. Good air circulation can help keep leaves dry. Get rid of any leaves that you have cut off or have fallen off as soon as possible.

Dust plants with sulfur powder every one to two weeks. This will not kill the rust, but will prevent germination of new spores. Spray a solution of one teaspoon of baking soda in one quart of water to help fight the rust. Foliar fungicides may also help. In one article, the author recommended using copper oxychloride. (Williams, 2020)

FIGURE 6 ALOE RUST

Sooty Mold

Our last condition is sooty mold. Sooty mold is a fungal infection that is secondary to an infestation of aphids or mealy bugs. Aphids and mealy bugs are pests that suck moisture out of plants and leave a clear, sticky substance called honeydew behind on the leaves. The honeydew creates a moist atmosphere that eventually develops into sooty mold. Sooty mold does not kill the plants; the insects will do that.

To address sooty mold, wash off the honeydew. This substance can be hard and lessen the amount of light reaching the leaves, reducing photosynthesis. (Williams, 2020)

FIGURE 7 SOOTY MOLD

17. Aloe Production Process

17.1 Cultivating & Harvesting

The cultivation of Aloe is influenced by a number of factors. Approximately 95% of the gel consists of water, therefore sufficient irrigation is required in good climatical conditions. Due to plants very small and shallow root base, has a limited capacity to absorb water and nutrients, therefore irrigation must be well designed and the soil properly fertilized. The advantage of growing Aloe is that the plant is resistant to all diseases, fungi, pests, locusts and grasshoppers. Additionally, the plant is not edible for animals such as goats, because of the bitter taste and laxative effects.¹¹ After the plants initial deployment phase and growth, the plant can be harvested 3 to 4 times a year. When harvesting, the bottom (largest) leaves have to be cut, on average this means 6 to 9 leaves per plant. A good leaf weighs between 700 and 900 grams each, preferably

more. Harvesting is a manual process. Plot management is crucial to control and maximize the yield of the plantation. (SHAHRIER, 2017)

17.2 Processing Leaves

After transport to the factory, the plants have to be washed and disinfected. There are two basic methods of processing: processing the entire leaf including the shell containing aloin (1- whole leaf method) and separating the leaf from the gel before processing (2- separation method). The Whole Leaf method leads, in our opinion, to an unacceptable finished product of low quality gel. In the separation method the bottom of the leaf is cut off and the leaves are left to "bleed". This leads to the aloin leaking out of the leaves. This is the part of the plant known for its bitter taste and its laxative effect. For a quality product, it is important that the aloin is kept out of the final gel. After some time of leaking, the process continues by cutting off the prickly edges with a sharp knife or a cheese grater type instrument. (SHAHRIER, 2017)

17.3 Separation Methods

After bleeding and the preparation process, the AGS machine is used for separating the gel from the leaf. The AGS machine is the most effective way of extracting the gel from the leaf.

17.4 Gel Processing

After the gel is removed from the plants it needs to be filtered, homogenized, pasteurized and stabilized. Through these processes, the gel changes from a transparent color to a honey brown color. The last step is then to concentrate the gel. The process from - cutting the leaves and the final Aloe extract - needs to be completed within a maximum of 2 days. Quality loss in the process can occur in a number of ways. The most important reasons are poor quality of leaves and poor or slow processing. Overall the following steps should be followed: (SHAHRIER, 2017)

1. Extracting Aloe gel from the leaves;
2. Filtration, homogenization, pasteurization and stabilization of the extracted Aloe gel;
3. Concentrating the Aloe gel. The result is a stabilized Aloe gel which is ready for use or further processing like concentrating a liquid or making a powder.

18. Extraction & Production Technique (Flow Chart) (SHAHRIER, 2017)

19. Conclusion The pharmacological attributes of *Aloe vera* have been revalidated in modern sciences through various in vivo and in vitro studies. These scientific studies are good enough proof that drug has immense potential as a dental therapeutic. So proper diagnosis, knowledge of the traditional medicine, and implementation of that knowledge to the treatment plan are important in ensuring success with this dental therapeutic agent. As a footnote, though *Aloe vera* is a promising herb with its various clinical applications in medicine and dentistry, the authors feels that more clinical research needs to be undertaken especially to validate and explain the action of acemannan hydrogel in accelerating the healing of aphthous ulcers and to validate the efficacy of *Aloe* gel on plaque and gingivitis, so that it can be established in the field of dentistry.

20. Aloe Vera Manufacturing Companies In Bangladesh

20.1. Taiwan Food Processing Ltd. (Shepherd Group) Corporate Office:

SHEPHERD TOWER

House # 24, Road # 4, Sector# 4 Uttara Model Town, Dhaka-1230, Bangladesh.

Phone: +880-2-7913340-42 Fax: + 880-2-7913359-60

E-mail: admin@shepherdbd.com

Factory Address: Bagrapara, Kathali, Bhaluka, Mymensingh, Bangladesh. Phone: +880-9022-56122-124 Fax: +880-9022-56288

20.2. Forever Living Products Bangladesh Bangladesh

Home Office: Jahangir Tower, (2nd Floor) 10 Kawranbazar, Dhaka-1215 Bangladesh

References

- (n.d.). *Aloe Vera Farming Guide*. AGRI FARMING. Retrieved from <https://www.agrifarming.in/aloe-vera-farming>
- Amar Surjushe, R. V. (2008). ALOE VERA: A SHORT REVIEW. *Indian J Dermatol*, 153-163.
- Atherton, D. P. (n.d.). *Aloe vera - The Medicine Plant*.
- Dalia I. Sanchez-Machado, J. L.-C.-S. (2017). Aloe vera: Ancient knowledge with new frontiers. *ELSEVIER*, 94-102.
- Sánchez-Machado, D. &.-C. (2017). Aloe vera: Ancient knowledge with new frontiers. Trends in Food Science & Technology. *ELSEVIER*, 94-102.
- SHAHRIER, A. (2017). *RESEARCH ON ALOE VERA CULTIVATION AND HARVESTING PROCESSES AND OUTPUT QUANTITY*. Personal Research.
- Williams, B. (2020). *Aloe Pests and Diseases*. Henry Shaw Cactus & Succulent Society. Retrieved from <https://hscactus.org/resources/digest/plant-care/aloe-pests-and-diseases/>